

The 55-nuclear charge triangular matrix of the first ten chemical elements Six non-bio-structural versus four bio-structural elements

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Abstract: It is demonstrated here that the first ten chemical elements oppose their nuclear charges, commonly called "atomic number Z " in an exact ratio of value $3/2$ depending on whether we consider some as non-bio-structural and others as bio-structural, this is to say more precisely as constituting or not canonical amino acid and of DNA nucleotides. We study here a triangular matrix of fifty-five entities which therefore represents the fifty-five nuclear charges of the first ten atoms. In relationship with number theory, many symmetrical and asymmetrical geometric sub-configurations of this triangular matrix show that these nuclear charges are distributed very singularly in various 3 to 2 value ratios. Hypothesis of the existence of proton boxes structuring the atomic nucleus and quantum orbitals analysis shows the same arithmetic phenomena.

Keywords: living matter, symmetry, nuclear charge, quantum orbitals, set theory, molecular biology, number theory.

1. Introduction

In several previous publications[1-2-3-4-5-6-7], we have been able to demonstrate that living matter, including more particularly the organization of the genetic code which governs it, is subject to numerical constraints. These digital algebra constraints very often reveal a partition of the elements structuring living matter in always an opposition of exact value $3/2$, so, also, with a full entity values equal to $5x$.

In the article "*Jean-Yves Boulay. The 55-entity triangular genetic code matrix and the 3 to 2 ratio. The genetic code as a geometric algebra biological system*" [1] we more particularly proposed the construction of a matrix of the genetic code reduced to 55 entities. With reference to number theory, we proposed a triangular matrix where the twenty different canonical amino acids are distributed, in a geometric algebra configuration. Here we propose the nuclear study of the first ten chemical elements. Our investigations focus more particularly on the nuclear charge, more commonly called the number Z of these first ten chemical elements.

From value 1, for Hydrogen, to value 10 for Neon, the accumulation of these Z numbers is arithmetically equal to 55, i.e. a triangular number with of T_{10} as size. We therefore find here the same geometric algebra value widely described in our previous paper just cited regarding a triangular matrix of the genetic code. The number 55 is very special in number theory. This is directly related to the decimal system. It is in fact a triangular number with value T_{10} . That is, it is the sum of the first strictly positive ten numbers from 1 to 10.

We highlight here that the first ten chemical elements can be separated into two sets: the non-bio-structural elements and the bio-structural elements. In a $3/2$ value ratio, among the first ten chemical elements, there are six non-bio-structural elements versus four bio-structural elements. Also, the cumulative number of nuclear charges of these two sets of atoms oppose each other in a ratio of exact value $3/2$ with 33 entities for the six non-bio-structural elements and 22 for the four bio-structural elements.

As the first ten elements contain a number of nuclear charges with triangular values T_{10} , we study here, as in our previous paper [1], a triangular matrix of 55 entities, matrix itself made up of sub-matrices of T_4 and T_5 as size.

Also, by exploiting the hypothesis of the existence of proton boxes structuring the atomic nucleus, we will further demonstrate the organization of the first ten chemical elements in arithmetic oppositions of exact value $3/2$ according to their non-bio-structural or bio-structural characteristics.

Finally, still considering the set of the first ten chemical elements, the quantum study of the distribution of electrons in a maximum of orbitals and therefore considering atoms in a maximum excited state, reveals the same oppositions in ratios of value $3/2$ of the orbitals according to the state of the electron spins filling them.

2. First ten chemical elements and living matter

As in previous paper about genetic code arrangement [1], here we find the value 55, a triangular number with value T_{10} , in a singular observation linking physics, biology and number theory.

2.1 Six non-bio-structural versus four bio-structural chemical elements

In prime mechanism of living matter, i.e. more simply the universal genetic code which is organized in DNA, RNA and twenty canonical amino acids, it turns out that only six bio-structural chemical elements (H, C, N, O, P and S) are used. Also, among

the first classified ten atoms (i.e. 5x elements), in a ratio of value 3/2, six are not bio-structural and four participate in the organization of living matter as constituents of the twenty canonical amino acids and also of the five nucleotides. These four bio-structural chemical elements are: Hydrogen, Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen. The cumulative value of the atomic numbers (Z), also called nuclear charge numbers, of the first ten elements is mathematically equal to 5x with $x = 11$, i.e. a cumulative charge equal to 55.

The first ten chemical elements:										
6 non-bio-structural chemical elements						← 3/2 ratio →	4 bio-structural chemical elements			
Helium	Lithium	Beryllium	Boron	Fluorine	Neon		Hydrogen	Carbon	Nitrogen	Oxygen
2	3	4	5	9	10		1	6	7	8
33 cumulated atomic numbers (33 protons)						← 3/2 ratio →	22 cumulated atomic numbers (22 protons)			

Figure 1: Opposition, in 3/2 ratios, of the 6 non-bio-structural chemical elements and 4 bio-structural chemical elements about their number and their respective cumulated atomic number (Z).

It is found, there again, that the cumulated value of the nuclear charges of the six non-bio-structural elements opposes that cumulated of the four bio-structural chemical elements in a ratio of exact value 3/2. Indeed, as shown in Figure 1, the six non-bio-structural elements total 33 nuclear charges (33 protons) and the four bio-structural elements which are Hydrogen, Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen total 22 nuclear charges (22 protons). Since all the other phenomena presented previously [1-2-3-4-5-6-7], it seems very unlikely that this ratio will appear there also by simple chance. The very singular new observations that we are going to introduce strongly support this idea.

2.2 The 55-entity triangular matrix of the first ten chemical elements

As we have already done with the table of the lighter genetic code and about the twenty canonical amino acids[1], we propose here a triangular matrix formed with the 55 cumulative charges (atomic numbers Z) of the first ten chemical elements.

Figure 2: Distribution of nuclear charges (atomic number) in a 55-entity triangular matrix according to non-bio-structural or bio-structural properties of the first ten chemical elements. See Figure 1 also.

In this matrix, each box represents a single nuclear charge or more simply one only proton. As we recall and as it is more visible in Figure 2, the 33 cumulative atomic numbers of the six non-bio-structural elements are opposed to the 22 cumulative atomic numbers of the four bio-structural elements. This, in a perfect arithmetic ratio of 3/2 as value.

2.3 Living matter and number theory

The number 55 is very special in number theory. This is directly related to the decimal system. It is in fact a triangular number with value T_{10} . That is, it is the sum of ten numbers from 1 to 10.

Also we recall that a triangular number is the sum of four other triangular numbers. So T_{10} is equal to $3T_5 + 1T_4$. Indeed, triangular number 55 is equal to $15 + 15 + 15 + 10$. Thus, the 55-entity triangular matrix of size T_{10} representing the cumulative atomic numbers of the first 10 elements can be symmetrically divided into four triangular areas of size T_5 or T_4 .

As illustrated in Figure 3, the symmetrical association of these areas two by two generates two sub-matrices of 25 and 30 entities where the non-bio-structural and bio-structural elements oppose their cumulative atomic number in exact ratio $3/2$.

Here the different values considered (18 versus 12 and 15 versus 10) remain the same as those previously presented in previous paper [1] throughout the numerous geometric algebra demonstrations made about amino acid distributions inside the 55-entity triangular genetic code matrix.

Figure 3: Opposition in perfect ratios of value $3/2$ of the cumulative atomic numbers of the non-bio-structural and bio-structural first ten chemical elements in symmetrical sub-matrices of sizes $2T_5$ and $T_5 + T_4$.

About this last 55-entity triangular matrix other numerous phenomena of geometric algebra similar or identical to those concerning the triangular matrix of the genetic code [1] operate.

3. Triangular matrix investigations

Values of the nuclear charges of chemical elements can be confused with their proton number. this is why, in the next demonstrations, we will speak more simply of protons to illustrate the distribution of nuclear charges (Z number) of the different elements studied.

3.1 Diagonal configurations

In Figure 4, the 55-proton triangular matrix is split into two subsets of 30 and 25 boxes. This is done by alternating the ten different diagonal lines of this matrix. In these two 5×5 entities areas, non-bio-structural charges and bio-structural charges oppose in exact $3/2$ ratios.

Figure 4: Distribution of non-bio-structural and bio-structural protons in 3 to 2 ratios into diagonal sub configurations of the 55-proton triangular matrix.

3.2 Mixed sub-configurations

Figure 5: Crossed sub-configurations of T_5 and T_4 as size with inside each, an exact ratio of value $\frac{3}{2}$ between the non-bio-structural protons and the bio-structural protons. See Figure 3, 4 and 6 also.

By crossing the triangular areas of Figure 3 (which are T_5 or T_4 in size) with diagonal configurations introduced in Figures 4, sub-configurations of size T_5 and T_4 are created. This creates, as illustrated in Figure 5, three sub-configurations of size T_5 (15 protons) and one of size T_4 (10 protons).

These four sub-configurations are more precisely the source of the triangular and diagonal configurations introduced previously. Indeed, their different associations produce the arrangements of Figures 3 and 4 which are $15 + 15$ entities ($T_5 + T_5$) or $15 + 10$ entities ($T_5 + T_4$) as size.

Within these four sub-configurations, the two sets nuclear charges (protons) described as non-bio-structural and bio-structural also oppose each other in an exact ratio of value $3/2$ with either 9 versus 6 protons or 6 versus 4 protons.

3.2.1 Mixed sub-configurations and remarkable identity

Inside central configuration of $15 + 10$ entities ($T_5 + T_4$) as size, The distribution of the 25 protons is arranged in the remarkable identity $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ where a and b have the respective values 3 and 2 (3 and 2 protons). Figure 6, complementing Figure 5, illustrates this singular arithmetic phenomenon.

Figure 6: According to non-bio-structural or bio-structural attributes (grey or white background) of the first ten atoms, remarkable identity revealed in the count of protons inside alternate sub-configurations of the triangular 25-proton matrix. See Figures 3 and 5 also. See Figure A4 in appendix to comparison.

4. Recombined 55-entity triangular matrix of the first ten chemical elements

We now offer a recombinant version of the previous 55-entity triangular matrix of the first ten chemical elements. As illustrated in Figure 7, here the different nuclear charges (atomic numbers Z) are distributed one after the other for each of the ten different elements. Thus, in this new triangular matrix, the first ten entities are those of the first ten different elements.

Then the next nine are atomic numbering elements 2 to 10, then 3 to 10, etc. We therefore find, in this other matrix, the 55 nuclear charges of the first 10 elements but in a different arrangement.

Figure 7: Distribution of nuclear charges (atomic number) in a 55-entity triangular matrix according to non-bio-structural or bio-structural properties of the first ten chemical elements. See Figure 1 also. See Figure 2 to comparison.

Although of a very different configuration regarding the distribution of the nuclear charges of the first ten chemical elements, in this new triangular matrix, the two sets of non-bio-structural or bio-structural protons oppose each other in exactly the same proportions as in the first matrix (introduced Figure 2). This considering the same geometric areas of size T_5 or T_4 .

4.1 Triangular sub-configurations of T_5 or T_4 as geometric size

Figure 8: Opposition in perfect ratios of value $3/2$ of the cumulative atomic numbers of the non-bio-structural and bio-structural first ten chemical elements in symmetrical sub-matrices of sizes $2T_5$ and $T_5 + T_4$. See Figure 3 to comparison.

Exactly as for the previous original triangular matrix, we divide this new triangular matrix of size T_{10} into four geometric areas of size T_5 or T_4 . As illustrated in Figure 8, the symmetrical association of these zones two by two generates two sub-matrices of 25 and 30 entities where the non-bio-structural and bio-structural elements oppose their cumulative atomic number in exact ratio $3/2$. Here the different values considered (18 versus 12 and 15 versus 10) remain the same as those previously presented.

4.2 Diagonal configurations

In Figure 9, and there also as it was done with the first matrix (introduced in Figure 2), this new 55-proton triangular matrix is split into two subsets of 30 and 25 boxes. This is done by alternating the ten different diagonal lines of this matrix. In these two $5x$ entities areas, non-bio-structural charges and bio-structural charges oppose in exact $3/2$ ratios.

Figure 9: Distribution of non-bio-structural and bio-structural protons in 3 to 2 ratios into diagonal sub configurations of the 55-proton triangular matrix. See Figure 4 for comparison.

4.3. Mixed sub-configurations

Figure 10: Crossed sub-configurations of T_5 and T_4 as size with inside each, an exact ratio of value 3/2 between the non-bio-structural protons and the bio-structural protons. See Figure 8 and 9 also. See Figure 5 to comparison.

Always similarly to the first triangular matrix, by crossing the triangular areas of Figure 8 (which are T_5 or T_4 in size) with diagonal configurations introduced in Figures 9, sub-configurations of size T_5 and T_4 are created. This creates, as illustrated in Figure 10, three sub-configurations of size T_5 (15 protons) and one of size T_4 (10 protons).

Within these four sub-configurations, the two sets nuclear charges (protons) described as non-bio-structural and bio-structural also oppose each other in an exact ratio of value $3/2$ with either 9 versus 6 protons or 6 versus 4 protons.

4.3.1 Mixed sub-configurations and remarkable identity

Identically as previous original configuration (introduced Figure 3), inside central configuration of $15 + 10$ entities ($T_5 + T_4$) size, The distribution of the 25 protons is arranged in the remarkable identity $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ where a and b have the respective values 3 and 2 (3 and 2 protons). Figure 11, complementing Figure 10, illustrates this singular arithmetic phenomenon.

Figure 11: According to non-bio-structural or bio-structural attributes (grey or white background) of the first ten atoms, remarkable identity revealed in the count of protons inside alternate sub-configurations of the triangular 25-proton matrix. See Figures 8 and 10 also. See Figure A4 in appendix to comparison.

5. Proton boxes hypothesis

Here we propose a nuclear study of chemical elements, including more particularly the first ten atoms using a new concept that we call "proton boxes". Like the concept of a quantum orbital which, concerning electronic shells, distributes electrons in pairs in different orbitals, we will similarly distribute the protons of each atom in "proton boxes". As for the orbitals, we therefore propose that the protons group together in quantum boxes of a maximum of two protons.

5.1 Triangular 30-proton box matrix

Thus, as illustrated in Figure 12, for example, the seven protons of the Nitrogen atom are distributed into four "proton boxes", three of which have two protons and one which has a single proton*. Also, for example, the eight protons of the Oxygen atom are distributed into four full "proton boxes" of two protons.

Figure 12: Distribution of protons of the first ten chemical elements in "proton boxes" of one and two entities. Geometric construction of a triangular matrix of 30 "proton boxes" describing the distribution of the 55 protons of the first ten chemical elements.

By this concept reminiscent of that of quantum orbitals, we propose a geometric construction of a triangular matrix of 30 "proton boxes" describing the distribution of the 55 protons of the first ten chemical elements.

Thus, this triangular matrix illustrated in the right part of Figure 12, represents a nuclear and quantum image of the first ten chemical elements. Also, the differentiation of non-bio-structural proton boxes from bio-structural ones is represented with the same code as in the previous illustrations: grey boxes for non-bio-structural elements and clear boxes for bio-structural ones.

By this concept of "proton boxes", similar algebra-geometric phenomena are revealed as those previously introduced and concerning the distribution of protons respectively non-bio-structural and bio-structural.

**In the illustrations of this concept of proton boxes, a black dot represents a proton, a white or grey dot represents the absence of a proton.*

We demonstrated above that the numbers of protons of the first ten atoms oppose each other in a ratio of value $3/2$ depending on whether these elements are non-bio-structural or bio-structural, i.e. 33 versus 22 nuclear charges.

Figure 13 allows us to observe that the proton boxes respective to these two groups of atoms are also in the same ratio with 18 proton boxes versus 12. Also and in more detail, the distinction between full proton boxes and semi full boxes still reveals this same $3/2$ value ratio.

Figure 13: Distribution of protons, proton boxes, full and semi full proton boxes of the first ten chemical elements in various $3/2$ ratios according to non-bio-structural or bio-structural properties of these ten atoms.

From the geometric construction of the triangular matrix introduced Figures 12 and 13, we propose, Figure 14, two symmetrical sub-matrices constructed by alternating thirty proton boxes which contain the 55 protons of the first ten classified atoms. thus these sub-matrices each contain 15 proton boxes.

Figure 14: According to non-bio-structural or bio-structural attributes (grey or white boxes), distribution in various 3 to 2 ratios of protons, proton boxes, full or semi full proton boxes into diagonal sub configurations of the triangular matrix of the first ten chemical elements.

This reveals a sophisticated distribution of the constituents of these chemical elements depending on whether they are non-bio-structural or bio-structural. Thus, in these two sub-matrices, both the protons and the proton boxes oppose each other in a perfect ratio of value 3/2. Also, the distinction between semi full proton boxes and full proton boxes continues to generate this same opposition of value 3/2 depending on whether the atoms concerned are non-bio-structural or bio-structural.

5.2 Full proton boxes and remarkable identity

By considering only the 25 full proton boxes of the triangular matrix just previously introduced, it appears that these boxes are organized into the remarkable identity $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ where a and b have the respective values 3 and 2.

Figure 15: According to non-bio-structural or bio-structural attributes (grey or white boxes) of the first ten atoms, remarkable identity revealed in the count of full proton boxes inside alternate sub-configurations of the triangular 30 proton boxes matrix without the five semi-full boxes. See Figures 13 and 14 also. See Figure A4 in appendix to comparison.

Thus, as illustrated in Figure 15, according to non-bio-structural or bio-structural attributes, the distribution of the full proton boxes inside diagonal sub configurations of the triangular matrix of the first ten chemical elements is constructed with the same proportional values as this remarkable identity.

In fact, in and between these two sub-configurations, 9 and 6 proton boxes (so a^2 and ab) then 6 and 4 proton boxes (so b^2 and ab) oppose each other. All this in entangled ratios of value 3/2.

In appendix, Figure A4, about shell and subshell amount of the five living matter atoms constituting canonical amino acids, an identical arithmetical phenomena can be observed.

6. Quantum analysis of atomic orbitals

After analyzing the distribution of nuclear charges (protons) of the first ten chemical elements, we will now study the quantum configuration of the orbitals and spins of these ten atoms, always differentiated into non-bio-structural and bio-structural. Here we propose to consider an unconventional state of atoms in a situation of extreme excitement.

The table in Figure 16 shows the electron configurations of chemical elements with atomic numbers Z from 1 to 10 in hypothetical highly excited states and in an optimal maximization of 5 orbitals. In these states, each electron of same spin (up or down) occupies a distinct orbital. This configuration, while representing an extremely high energy state and violating the Aufbau principle, adheres to the Pauli Exclusion Principle by placing each electron in a unique quantum state.

Although very singular, these configurations of orbitals and electronic spins remain in accordance with the principles of quantum physics pushed here to the extreme for these first ten chemical elements.

elements	Z	orbitals				
Hydrogen	1	↑				
Helium	2	↑	↑			
Lithium	3	↑	↑	↑		
Beryllium	4	↑	↑	↑	↑	
Boron	5	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Carbon	6	↑ ↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
Nitrogen	7	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑	↑	↑
Oxygen	8	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑	↑
Fluorine	9	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑
Neon	10	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑ ↓	↑ ↓

Figure 16: Highly excited states of elements (Z=1-10) optimized to a maximum of five orbitals. Non-bio-structural elements are highlighted by a grey background. See Figure 17 also.

The choice to consider ten chemical elements, in this case the first ten elements (Z=1-10) deployed on 5 quantum orbitals is not trivial. We therefore consider here $5x$ entities ($2x \rightarrow x = 5$) with $5x$ components ($1x \rightarrow x = 5$). We therefore strongly link quantum physics and number theory here.

First 10 chemical elements	→	6 non-bio-structural elements	← 3/2 ratio →	4 bio-structural elements
50 orbitals	□	30 orbitals	← 3/2 ratio →	20 orbitals
10 empty orbitals	□	6 orbitals	← 3/2 ratio →	4 orbitals
40 full or semi full orbitals	↑↓ or ↑	24 orbitals	← 3/2 ratio →	16 orbitals
25 semi full orbitals	↑	15 orbitals	← 3/2 ratio →	10 orbitals
15 full orbitals	↑ ↓	9 orbitals	← 3/2 ratio →	6 orbitals
55 spins (55 electrons)	↑ or ↓	33 spins	← 3/2 ratio →	22 spins
40 spins up (40 electrons)	↑	24 spins ↑	← 3/2 ratio →	16 spins ↑
15 spins down (15 electrons)	↓	9 spins ↓	← 3/2 ratio →	6 spins ↓

Figure 17: Orbital and spin distribution of the first ten elements distinguished into non-bio-structural and bio-structural. See Figure 16 also.

As illustrated in Figure 17 which summarizes in detail what emerges from the electronic configurations presented in Figure 16, the different entities considered are all globally equal to $5x$: $5x$ orbitals, $5x$ full orbitals, $5x$ spins, etc. and from this, all the different quantum entities considered always oppose each other in a value ratio of $3/2$ between the two sets of 6 and 4 atoms respectively qualified as non-bio-structural or bio-structural.

Continuing this analysis of the proposed fifty orbital mapping, we can isolate two sets of 25 entities of equal size. As illustrated in Figure 18, there are thus 25 semi-full orbitals (25 spins up) versus 25 others either empty or full. For these two sets, the atoms qualified as non-bio-structural and bio-structural oppose each other in ratios of exact value $3/2$. This, both considering, for these 10 different chemical elements, the orbital numbers and the two spin categories.

50 orbitals ($5x$ orbitals $\rightarrow x = 10$)
 55 electron spins ($5x$ spins $\rightarrow x = 11$)

Figure 18: According to the filling of the orbitals and in highly excited states of elements ($Z=1-10$) optimized to a maximum of five orbitals, non-bio-structural elements (highlighted by a grey background) and bio-structural elements are opposed in 3 to 2 ratios. This for orbital categories and spins categories. See Figures 16 and 17 also.

6.1 Quantum physics and remarkable identity

We have repeatedly highlighted, in this analysis of the first ten chemical elements, a singular relationship between the collective arrangement of their quantum attributes and the remarkable mathematical identity $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ where a and b have the respective values 3 and 2.

Once again and as illustrated in Figure 19, we note that the set of 15 full orbitals ($\uparrow\downarrow$) and that of 10 empty orbitals are organized in transcendent ratios of 3/2 as value considering the non-bio-structurality or bio-structurality of the chemical elements considered.

Thus, organized in a remarkable identity, these 25 ($\rightarrow (a + b)^2$) orbitals are decomposed into:

- 9 ($\rightarrow a^2$) non-bio-structural full orbitals,
- 6 ($\rightarrow ab$) bio-structural full orbitals,
- 6 ($\rightarrow ab$) non-bio-structural empty orbitals,
- 4 ($\rightarrow b^2$) bio-structural empty orbitals.

Figure 19: According to non-bio-structural or bio-structural attributes (grey or white boxes) of the first ten atoms, remarkable identity revealed in the count of empty and full orbitals inside the 50-orbital quantum matrix of the first 10 chemical elements. See Figures 16 and 17 also. See Figure A4 in appendix to comparison.

7. Domination of the 3/2 ratio in living matter organization

As a preliminary conclusion, it seems essential to us to speak about the importance of the arithmetic ratio of value 3/2 in the organization of the genetic code and more largely in the organization of the living matter.

In a preview paper "*Genetic code, quantum physics and the 3/2 ratio*" [5], we have revealed in great detail, a multitude of arithmetic arrangements of the components of the genetic code in this 3/2 ratio.

For example, we are drawing attention to the fact that Glycine, which is simply like an amino acid base, has all these various components at 5x in number (10 atoms, 40 protons, 75 nucleons, etc.) and that these can be opposed in 3x and 2x in number.

Also in this paper [5], the same phenomena are also observed in the composition of the five atoms constituting the twenty proteinogenic amino acids (Hydrogen, Carbon, Nitrogen, Oxygen and Sulphur) which can also be opposed in various ratios of 3/2 values.

In a other preview paper "*Numbering of the twenty proteinogenic amino acids and new alphanumerical nomenclature proposal to them*" [2], We have demonstrated a powerful organization of the different attributes of the twenty canonical amino acids (5x in number or 3x + 2x) in perfect arithmetic arrangements of value 3/2 according to their associated genetic coding.

These many observations confirm the main idea of this article that the genetic code, confused AAs and nucleobases, is arithmetically organized according with the ratio 3/2. Some of these singular phenomena are more fully illustrated in the appendix at the end of this paper.

Also, various other genetic code investigations from many authors are in relationship with the subject of this paper especially about ratio 3 to 2, symmetry, listing of proteinogenic amino acids or more generally connections between number theory and the genetic code. As example and not limited to, some of these investigations are listed in references [8 to 21].

From this reference list, we draw particular attention to two of our previous preprints. In “*Preproinsulin molecule and numbering of the twenty proteinogenic amino acids*” [6], we demonstrate that the amino acid sequence of the 110-amino acid preproinsulin, the initial product of the translation of insulin mRNA, is in close dependence with the twice concept of the numbering of the twenty proteinogenic amino acids and the ultimate genetic code. In fact, It turns out that the orders of occurrence of the various preproinsulin amino acids, both direct and inverse sequence, are organized in numerous ratios of exact value $3/2$. This, according to the amino acid numbering concept. The degree of abundance of these amino acids in this initial single-chain molecule reveals same numerical rational phenomena.

In “*Amino acid numbering, ultimate numbers and the $3/2$ ratio*” [7], we demonstrate relationships between the mechanism of the genetic code, of the field of Biology, and the number theory field, of which more precisely the notion of *ultimate number* [18 and 19], one of the four classes of Mathematics entities proposed to constitute the set of whole numbers. These connections are revealed in an physico-arithmetic organization of the genetic code in various ratios of $3/2$ value as global configurations.

8. Discussions and conclusions

In our previous numerous publications, we have largely demonstrated that living matter is organized according to algebraic-numerical constraints with global values equal to $5x$ and blocks of intermediate and interactive values respectively equal to $3x$ and $2x$.

In these previous investigations, a strong relationship between the biological organization of matter and number theory became clear. We have more particularly demonstrated a strong dependence of living matter on the decimal system articulated with the numerical value five, then ten as the main multiple. It is therefore quite natural that we have concentrated our study of life here on the nuclear investigation of the first ten chemical elements. Indeed, the different chemical elements are also, and entirely under the constraint of numerical criteria, differentiating them.

The first ten atoms therefore have from one to ten protons in their atomic nucleus, or from one to ten nuclear charges, this is their specific quantum characteristic. In connection with the field of arithmetic, they therefore total fifty-five nuclear charges so $5x$ entities with x equal to 11. This value is therefore a triangular number with value T_{10} and so, the study of a triangular matrix of this size which geometrically lists these charges or protons is very legitimate.

We therefore demonstrate that the geometric distribution of nuclear charges within this triangular matrix and according to different symmetrical sub-configurations is organized in a ratio of value 3 to 2 depending on whether the different atoms are of non-bio-structural or bio-structural nature. This is revealed just as much, considering the distribution of electronic spins in a quantum configuration pushed to the extreme for these first ten chemical elements of which we will greatly draw attention to the fact that 6 are non-bio-structural and 4 are bio-structural.

We once again make the observation of highlighting this “universal ratio” in the organization of living matter. Also in the ambitious hypothesis of the quantum existence of proton boxes, we always observe the same arithmetic phenomenon. Furthermore, we find an arithmetic mechanics identical to that already revealed in a previous quantum study [5], of the five elements constituting the twenty canonical amino acids by the observation of an articulation entangled in a remarkable identity.

This new demonstration reinforces all our previous introduced papers [1-2-3-4-5-6-7], revealing each time and under numerous aspects an organization of living matter into digital entities. Thus, although, at base, these are physico-chemical properties, we can proclaim that living matter, in its genetic organization, in reality uses purely mathematical mechanisms.

This may open the way to a new branch of science considering living matter as a pure algebra biological system. Also, since this sophisticated mathematical organization of living matter depends on the physical properties of the chemical elements generated since the Big Bang, we can say, with strong conviction, that it is the purpose of cosmic evolution.

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APPENDIX

Many of phenomena presented here are taken from the author's previous paper: *Jean-Yves Boulay. Genetic code, quantum physics and the 3/2 ratio. 2020. [5]*. Other phenomena is from various J-Y Boulay papers listed in references. This appendix is of a global theme and sometimes without direct references to the different chapters introduced previously. Its important relationship, however, is the organization of the genetic code around a numerical constraint revealed in an exact ratio of value 3 to 2.

A1. Anatomy of Glycine as 3/2 ratio

A1.1 Glycine as glycined base

Within the mechanism of the genetic code and therefore among the twenty amino acids, Glycine is distinguished by its absence of radical. Its radical is reduced to a simple hydrogen atom which in a way simply closes the "base" structure common to each amino acid. The quantum study of this *glycined base*, identifying with Glycine, reveals singular arithmetic arrangements of its different components.

A1.2 Modules of Petoukhov

The notion of modules is an original system proposed by Sergey Petoukhov [8 and 10] to describe the structure of biological molecules. According to this genetic code researcher, in organic chemistry, module is a group formed of just one non-hydrogen

atom with possibly its satellite hydrogen atoms attached. Also, Sergey Petoukhov considers Sulphur as constituted in a twice module.

A1.3 Detailed structure of Glycine

Figure A1 describes the structure of Glycine (or saturated base called *glycined base*) according to many criteria including its chemical composition, modular, but also atomic. It turns out that Glycine consists of 40 protons, either $5x$ protons or $(3 + 2)x$ protons.

This glycined base also consists of 5 groups or modules, i.e. $(3 + 2)x$ chemical groups. In Glycine, the number of protons is therefore an exact multiple of 8 (5 times 8 protons) and it turns out that the average number of protons per chemical group (or Petoukhov module) is therefore 8. For two groups (CH₂ and O), the amount of protons is exactly 8 whereas for the other three groups, these proton amounts are 9 or 6 (NH₂ → 9, OH → 9 and C → 6). The differentiation of these two types of modules, made up or not made up of 8 protons reveals a multitude of oppositions of the different natures of the components of Glycine (glycined base) in always an arithmetical ratio of 3/2 value.

Figure A1: Chemical, modular and atomic structure of a saturated base identified with the amino acid Glycine: 5 modules, 10 atoms, 40 protons and 35 neutrons. See also Figure A2. * inspired representation from Sergey Petoukhov [8 and 10].

Glycine is made up of a multitude of entities whose numbers are all multiples of five. Thus the glycined base consists of five modules, two times five atoms, five of which have one electron shell (H) and five at two shells (C, N and O). Also Glycine consists of 5 times 15 nucleons (75) including 5 times 7 (35) neutrons and 5 times 8 (40) protons. Valences of these different components are also in numbers which are equal to $5x$ entities.

Glycine entities	Total entities number	Entities account in 3 no 8-proton modules	Entities account in 2 8-proton modules
5 modules	5 $5x \rightarrow x = 1$	3 $3x \rightarrow x = 1$	2 $2x \rightarrow x = 1$
10 atoms	10 $5x \rightarrow x = 2$	6 $3x \rightarrow x = 4$	4 $2x \rightarrow x = 4$
5 non-hydrogen atoms (at even number quantum shells)	5 $5x \rightarrow x = 1$	3 $3x \rightarrow x = 1$	2 $2x \rightarrow x = 1$
5 hydrogen atoms (at odd number quantum shells)	5 $5x \rightarrow x = 1$	3 $3x \rightarrow x = 1$	2 $2x \rightarrow x = 1$
75 nucleons	75 $5x \rightarrow x = 15$	45 $3x \rightarrow x = 15$	30 $2x \rightarrow x = 15$
40 protons	40 $5x \rightarrow x = 8$	24 $3x \rightarrow x = 8$	16 $2x \rightarrow x = 8$
35 neutrons	35 $5x \rightarrow x = 7$	21 $3x \rightarrow x = 7$	14 $2x \rightarrow x = 7$
20 valences (cumulated by atom)	20 $5x \rightarrow x = 4$	12 $3x \rightarrow x = 4$	8 $2x \rightarrow x = 4$
15 valences in non-hydrogen atoms	15 $5x \rightarrow x = 3$	9 $3x \rightarrow x = 3$	6 $2x \rightarrow x = 3$
5 valences in hydrogen atoms	5 $5x \rightarrow x = 1$	3 $3x \rightarrow x = 1$	2 $2x \rightarrow x = 1$

Figure A2: Distribution of the prime attributes (to $5x$ in number) of Glycine. Arrangement in $3/2$ ratios according to module proton number which can be equal to 8 or not to 8.

Also, it therefore appears, Figures A1 and A2, that the different constituents of Glycine, always $5x$ in number, are always at 3 same x entities in the set of three modules (chemical groups) with number of protons not equal to 8 and always of amount at 2 same x entities in the set of two modules whose number of protons is equal to 8.

A2. Five living matter atoms

Canonical amino acids (and nucleotides) are just constituted by arrangements of five different atoms. The opposition of the values of Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen to those of Hydrogen and Sulphur (Phosphorus for nucleotides in DNA), always generates an arithmetic ratio of value $3/2$ according to multiple criteria studied.

A2.1 Quantum anatomy of the five living matter atoms

The table in Figure A3 lists the impressive series of quantum situations in which this remarkable duality takes place between sets of $3x$ entities versus $2x$ entities. Thus, the ratio for the numbers of electron subshells ($1s, 2s, 2p, 3s, 3p$) is $3/2$. It is still $3/2$ if we detail the subshells of those where the quantum number $l = 0$ of those where the quantum number $l = 1$. Also, the ratio for the numbers of orbitals is $3/2$. It is still on $3/2$ if we detail the orbitals of those where the quantum number $m = 0$, of those where the quantum number $m = -1$ and those where the quantum number $m = 1$.

This ratio is always $3/2$ if we detail the orbitals of those where the quantum number $l = 0$ of those where the quantum number $l = 1$. Also, the maximum number of electrons that can orbit inside all of the electronic shells of these two groups of atoms is still in a ratio of $3/2$: thirty electrons can orbit inside the electronic shells of Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen versus twenty on the electron shells of Hydrogen and Sulphur (Phosphorus for DNA bases).

Quantum criteria:	Atoms to even number of electron quantum shells			Atoms to odd number of electron quantum shells	
	Carbon 1	Nitrogen 1	Oxygen 1	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 1
Number of atoms	3 atoms			2 atoms	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
Number of electron shells (K, L, M)	Carbon 2	Nitrogen 2	Oxygen 2	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 3
	6 electron shells			4 electron shells	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
Number of subshells (1s, 2s, 2p, 3s, 3p)	Carbon 3	Nitrogen 3	Oxygen 3	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 5
	9 subshells			6 subshells	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
Number of subshells where the quantum number $l = 0$	Carbon 2	Nitrogen 2	Oxygen 2	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 3
where the quantum number $l = 1$	1	1	1	0	2
	6 subshells where $l = 0$			4 subshells where $l = 0$	
	3 subshells where $l = 1$			2 subshells where $l = 1$	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
Maximum number of orbitals	Carbon 5	Nitrogen 5	Oxygen 5	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 9
	15 orbitals			10 orbitals	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
Number of orbitals where the quantum number $m = 0$	Carbon 3	Nitrogen 3	Oxygen 3	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 5
where the quantum number $m = -1$	1	1	1	0	2
where the quantum number $m = 1$	1	1	1	0	2
	9 orbitals where $m = 0$			6 orbitals where $m = 0$	
	3 orbitals where $m = -1$			2 orbitals where $m = -1$	
	3 orbitals where $m = +1$			2 orbitals where $m = +1$	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
	← 3/2 ratio →				
	← 3/2 ratio →				
number of orbitals where the quantum number $l = 0$	Carbon 2	Nitrogen 2	Oxygen 2	Hydrogen 1	Sulphur* 3
where the quantum number $l = 1$	3	3	3	0	6
	6 orbitals where $l = 0$			4 orbitals where $l = 0$	
	9 orbitals where $l = 1$			6 orbitals where $l = 1$	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
	← 3/2 ratio →				
Maximum number of electrons orbiting on quantum shells	Carbon 10	Nitrogen 10	Oxygen 10	Hydrogen 2	Sulphur* 18
of which the first shell (internal)	2	2	2	2	2
of which the outer shell (s)	8	8	8	-	8+8
	30 electrons			20 electrons	
	6 electrons			4 electrons	
	24 electrons			16 electrons	
	← 3/2 ratio →				
	← 3/2 ratio →				
	← 3/2 ratio →				

Figure A3: 3/2 ratio of the electron shells and subshells, orbitals and maximum numbers of electrons according to the parity of the number of electron shells of the five atoms constituting the twenty amino acids (* Or Phosphorus for DNA).
Other 3/2 ratios generated in relation to the values of the different quantum numbers of the electrons.

For this last criterion, the distinction of the electrons which can orbit either on the first internal shell (2 electrons for each of the five atoms) or on the set of the other (external) shells always opposes the different values in ratios 3/2: 6 versus 4 electrons for the inner shell and 24 versus 16 for the other shells.

Thus, fourteen different quantum criteria oppose, in a duality of ratio 3/2, the five atoms constituting the twenty amino acids (and also constituting the four DNA nucleotides with the Phosphorus in place of Sulphur). The fact that the genetic code is organized only with these five different atoms in this duality is therefore not random. The perfect complementarity of the quantum characteristics of Hydrogen and Sulphur (Phosphorus in DNA) is particularly remarkable.

These last two atoms have indeed very different quantum characteristics (in contrast to Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen with common characteristics) which however complement each other perfectly to always oppose in a 3/2 ratio to three other atoms, constituents of amino acids (and DNA bases). For example, Sulphur has a maximum number of nine orbitals versus only one for Hydrogen. These two very different values nevertheless complement each other (10 orbitals) to oppose in a duality of ratio 3/2 to the three times five quantum orbitals of Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen (15 orbitals).

Thus, the 3/2 ratio is revealed at the bottomest of the subatomic structure of the constituents of the twenty amino acids that are on the one hand the three atoms of Carbon, Nitrogen and Oxygen and on the other hand the two atoms of Hydrogen and Sulphur. It is therefore remarkable to note that these same phenomena are found in DNA, another mechanical component of the genetic code, where the quantum properties of the Phosphorus mimic those of Sulphur.

A2.2 Five living matter atoms and remarkable identity

Thus, these various ratios opposing the subshells and shells and transversely, the two categories of atoms previously defined according to the parity of their number of quantum shells, are organized in the remarkable identity $(a + b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ where a and b have the respective values 3 and 2.

Figure A4 explains this arithmetic organization operating in the quantum structure of the five elements working within the genetic code.

Figure A4: Remarkable identity revealed in the count of subshells and quantum shells of the five elements H, C, N, O and S (*or P in DNA). See Figure A3. See Figures 11, 15 and 19 to comparison.

Thus, the quantity of subshells in C, N and O corresponds to the value a^2 of the remarkable identity and the quantity of subshells in H and S corresponds to the value ab . The quantity of quantum shells in C, N and O also corresponds to the value ab and that in H and S corresponds to the value b^2 . These different values therefore transcend into these equal ratios:

$$(a^2/ab) = (ab/b^2) = (a^2+ab)/(ab+b^2)$$

$$(3^2/6) = (6/2^2) = (3^2+6)/(6+2^2)$$

$$(9/6) = (6/4) = (15)/(10)$$

It is important here to emphasize the perfect similarity of the ratios and values with what is presented in Figure 13 about the full proton boxes of the first ten chemical elements.

In a similar fashion, this remarkable identity therefore also operates in the counts of electrons according to their azimuthal quantum number and according to their magnetic number. In these electron counts, the values are just double and, for a and b at the root values 3 and 2, the respective and transcendent values are equal to:

$$2a^2 \rightarrow 2ab \rightarrow 2ab \rightarrow 2b^2$$

$$18 \rightarrow 12 \rightarrow 12 \rightarrow 8$$

A4. Numbering of the twenty canonical amino acids

Here a condensed view of the article which is published in the journal *Symmetry: Culture and Science* [2].

A4.1 Some prime amino acid attributes.

The table in Figure A5 condenses the main values relating to the twenty proteinogenic amino acids. This table lists absolute (integer) values which are therefore not suggestive and subject to debate. For each amino acid, it is so listed, its numbering, its atom number inside its radical, detail of this number with atoms at even or odd electron shells, its number of CH₂ groups (methylene bridges directly connected to alpha carbon).

It is also listed, for each of twenty proteinogenic amino acids, its rank of OMH hydrophobicity index [20] and its number of codons in its largest respective codon set with two first same DNA bases.

A brief overview of this table already demonstrates the powerful tendency of the mechanism of the genetic code to organize itself into perfect arithmetic ratios of 3/2 values. We study here from the outset, both the anatomy of amino acids (physical structure), their chemical properties (hydrophobicity) and the coding genetic structure associated with them. This voluntary approach in order to suggest the inter connectivity of the phenomena studied.

AA	Molecular formula*	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>g</i>
Gly	H	0	1	0	1	0	15	4
Val	C3H7	1	10	3	7	0	6	4
Trp	C9H8N	2	18	10	8	1	7	1
Cys	CH3S	3	5	1	4	1	8	2
Leu	C4H9	4	13	4	9	1	4	4
Phe	C7H7	5	14	7	7	1	1	2
Glu	C3H5O2	6	10	5	5	2	19	2
Asp	C2H3O2	7	7	4	3	1	20	2
Ala	CH3	8	4	1	3	0	10	4
Tyr	C7H7O	9	15	8	7	1	2	2
Ser	CH3O	10	5	2	3	1	12	4
Arg	C4H10N3	11	17	7	10	3	13	4
Met	C3H7S	12	11	3	8	2	5	1
Ile	C4H9	13	13	4	9	0	3	3
Lys	C4H10N	14	15	5	10	4	16	2
Asn	C2H4NO	15	8	4	4	1	18	2
Thr	C2H5O	16	8	3	5	0	9	4
Gln	C3H6NO	17	11	5	6	2	17	2
His	C4H5N2	18	11	6	5	1	14	2
Pro	C3H6	19	9	3	6	3	11	4
Cumulated values		190	205	85	120	25	210	55
12 external values (from 0 to 5 and from 14 to 19)		114	123	51	72	15	126	33
8 internal values (from 6 to 13)		76	82	34	48	10	84	22
ratio →		3/2						

a numbering of the twenty amino acids**

b number of atoms in the radical

c number of atoms with an even number of electron shells (C, N and O)

d number of atoms with a odd number of electron shells (H and S)

e number of CH₂ groups (methylene bridge directly connected to alpha carbon)

f rank of OMH hydrophobicity index[20]: rank from the highest index to the lowest index

g number of codons in largest codon sets with 2 first same DNA bases

Figure A5: Some prime amino acid attributes.*Radical only and in non-ionized state. **From papers [2-3].

A4.2 Alphanumeric symbol of the 20 proteinogenic amino acids

We have therefore firmly established, in many aspects, that the various characteristics of the twenty canonical proteinogenic amino acids are closely linked to their numbering, which itself depends on their DNA codification as proposed at the beginning of the article. This is why we suggest here, to enrich the current nomenclature applied to these twenty entities, the creation of new standardized alphanumeric symbols making it possible to identify these twenty proteinogenic amino acids.

In first preview papers [2 and 3], we initially numbered these entities from 0 to 19 and we attached their respective number to their three-letter alphabetic symbol. For example, we have described Valine as *IVal* and Arginine as *IIArg* so by respectively four and five characters.

For the sake of standardization (and even formalization), we propose, as illustrated Figures A6 and A7, to describe all the twenty AAs with five characters, two of which are numeric and three alphabetical. So we add the number symbol 0 (zero) to the first ten AAs numbered from 0 to 9. By this, for each AA, we therefore propose a unified symbol of 2 digits + 3 letters.

Conventional nomenclature		Proposed alphanumeric symbol into 5 characters	
Trivial name	→	<i>Glycine</i>	
Symbol (three letters)	→	<i>Gly</i>	→ 00Gly
One letter symbol	→	<i>G</i>	

Figure A6: Conventional nomenclature and alphanumeric symbol proposal to proteinogenic amino acids into 5 characters: 2 digits + 3 letters. Here Glycine as example. See Figure A7 also.

Figure A7 therefore lists all of the 20 proteinogenic amino acids involved in the mechanism of the universal genetic code. It is table therefore described, from the conventional nomenclature, the trivial name, the symbol in 3 letters and the one letter symbol. To this is added, for each AA, its alphanumeric symbol of 5 characters that we propose as a new standardized and official nomenclature.

The 20 proteinogenic amino acids conventional nomenclature:			Alphanumeric symbol proposal
<i>Trivial name</i>	<i>symbol</i>	<i>one letter symbol</i>	
Glycine	Gly	G	00Gly
Valine	Val	V	01Val
Tryptophan	Trp	W	02Trp
Cysteine	Cys	C	03Cys
Leucine	Leu	L	04Leu
Phenylalanine	Phe	F	05Phe
Glutamic acid	Glu	E	06Glu
Aspartic acid	Asp	D	07Asp
Alanine	Ala	A	08Ala
Tyrosine	Tyr	Y	09Tyr
Serine	Ser	S	10Ser
Arginine	Arg	R	11Arg
Methionine	Met	M	12Met
Isoleucine	Ile	I	13Ile
Lysine	Lys	K	14Lys
Asparagine	Asn	N	15Asn
Threonine	Thr	T	16Thr
Glutamine	Gln	Q	17Gln
Histidine	His	H	18His
Proline	Pro	P	19Pro

Figure A7: Conventional nomenclature and alphanumeric symbol proposal to the twenty proteinogenic amino acids into 5 characters: 2 digits + 3 letters.